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1 Introduction

The goal of this paper is to take concepts presented in Displays for Teichmüller spaces (Buchanan, 2023) and connect them to the forms of Energy Numbers presented in Limbertwig (Emmerson, 2023) to generate a complete transitional kernel with definitions in terms of the Energy Numbers and relevant topological mapping solve methods.

$$\Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m} \rightarrow_{\Gamma} \kappa \simeq (C(S))' \rightarrow C(S)_{\text{DISC}}$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \leftarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m - l^m} \right) + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) = \sum_{h \leftarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h.$$

$$n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}.$$

This equation can be rearranged into:

$$\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi = \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m} \Rightarrow n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}$$

Therefore, the solution to the equation is:

$$\Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m} \rightarrow_{\Gamma} \kappa \simeq (C(S))' \rightarrow C(S)_{\text{DISC}}$$

where

$$\phi_n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}$$

$$\mathcal{P}_{\Omega} = \tanh(\Omega_{\Lambda}^{\phi_n^m}) \rightarrow_{\Gamma} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \leftarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m - l^m}}{\Omega_{\Lambda}^{\phi_n^m}}.$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{\phi_n^m} = \Omega_{\Lambda}^{\phi_n^m} \rightarrow_{\Gamma} \tanh(\Omega_{\Lambda}^{\phi_n^m}) + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) = \sum_{h \leftarrow \infty} \tan \psi \diamond \theta \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h.$$

Thus

$$\Omega_{\phi_n^b}^{\phi_m^b} \rightarrow_{\Gamma} \kappa \simeq (C(S))' \rightarrow C(S)_{\text{DISC}} \mathcal{P}_{\Omega} + \mathcal{Q}_{\phi_n^m} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \leftarrow \infty} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{n^m - l^m}}{\tanh(\Omega_{\Lambda}^{\phi_n^m}) + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}$$

Finally to solve for the product $C(S)_{\text{DISC}}$, we use the rule of product of powers:

$$(C(S))' \rightarrow C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = \Omega_{\phi_n^b}^{\phi_m^b \cdot r}$$

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = \Omega_{\phi_n^b \cdot f'}^{\phi_m^b \cdot r}$$

Where f' and r are the radicals corresponding to numerator and denominator of the fraction, respectively.

Using the theorem above, the final result is

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = K \cdot \Omega_{\phi_n^b}^{\phi_m^b} \cdot K^{-1}$$

where

$$\phi_n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}$$

. and $K = \partial_{\text{SET}}(\mathbb{P})$ is a completion of $\mathbb{T}$.

where $K = \partial_{\text{SET}}(\mathbb{P})$ is a completion of $\mathbb{T}$, such that the product $\Omega_{\phi_n^b \cdot f'}^{\phi_m^b \cdot r}$ can be expressed as

$$\Omega_{\phi_n^b \cdot f'}^{\phi_m^b \cdot r} = K \cdot \Omega_{\phi_n^b}^{\phi_m^b} \cdot K^{-1} \rightarrow C(S)_{\text{DISC}}$$

Therefore, $C(S)_{\text{DISC}}$ can be expressed as:

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = K \cdot \Omega_{\phi_n^b}^{\phi_m^b} \cdot K^{-1}$$

where

$$\phi_n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}$$

. $\partial_{\text{SET}}(\mathbb{P}) < \text{Hom}(C(S), \text{coord})$ is the completion of $\mathbb{T}$, which yields the product of completion and transitional kernel, such that

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = \partial_{\text{SET}}(\mathbb{P}) < \Omega_{\phi_n^b}^{\phi_m^b} >_K .$$

$P: V_{\text{psh}} \rightarrow V_{\text{shv}}$ is a functional parameter that maps from a point set Hausdorff topological space to a separated Hausdorff topological space. It is used to compute the product of completion and translucent kernel matrix.

where $f_i \in V_{\text{psh}}$ and $\iota \in T$. The product $\Pi \iota$ is then used to compute the product of completion and translucent kernel matrix

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = \partial_{\text{SET}}(P) \langle \Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m^b} \rangle_{\text{K}}$$

$$\text{where } \phi_n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}.$$

Where Π is a symbolic integration formula. The integral is a mathematical symbol which defines composition rule between sets.

$$C = C(S)_{\text{DISC}} \star f \star \iota = \partial_{\text{SET}}(P) \langle \Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m^b} \rangle_{\text{K}} \star f \star \iota \rightarrow C(S)_{\text{DISC}}$$

where $C(S)_{\text{DISC}}$ is the product of completion and translucent kernel matrix and the complete solution is:

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = \partial_{\text{SET}}(P) \langle \Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m^b} \rangle_{\text{K}} \star f \star \iota$$

where

$$\phi_n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}$$

Theorem 3.0.3 Let T_g be an algebraic space with underlying topological space $T_g \rightarrow_{\text{pt}} \partial(U(\varepsilon))$ and let q_{filt} be the principal ultrafilter on E . Then, the completion of T_g is given by

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = \partial_{\text{SET}}(P) \langle \Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m^b} \rangle_{\text{K}} \star f \star \iota,$$

where

$$\phi_n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}$$

The proof of this theorem follows directly from Definitions 3.0.1 and 3.0.2 and the discussion which followed them.

$$\widehat{B}_{\tau < 1}^{\downarrow} \rightarrow \text{Topo}_{q\text{Disc}_{\tau > 0}} \rightarrow \text{qCoh}(L_{\varepsilon}) \rightarrow {}^L\mathbf{B}^R \leftarrow \text{qCoh}(L_{\varepsilon}^R) \leftarrow \text{Topo}_{q\text{Disc}_{\tau > 0}}$$

Where $\widehat{B}_{\tau < 1}^{\downarrow}$ is the factor space of two explicitly lensed displays mapping from a point set Hausdorff topological space to a separated Hausdorff topological space, and $\text{qCoh}(L_{\varepsilon}^R)$ is the quantity of coherence allowing an effective exact equivalence between analytic cosheafs as an arithmetic sum of subbrings, with the arithmetic distance $d(L_{\varepsilon}, \varepsilon^R)$ between them of the form $\frac{2q_{\text{fit}}+1}{q_i-1}$. Thus, the complete solution is given by

$$C(S)_{\text{DISC}} = \partial_{\text{SET}}(P) \langle \Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m^b} \cdot f \star \iota \rangle_{\text{K}}$$

where

$$\phi_n = \sqrt[m]{\frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{\frac{1}{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h} - \Psi}}.$$

From the display notion, we can derive the notion of a "synchronism", which is a generalization of the Witt vector displays. Synchronisms are defined as a triple $(M, \mathcal{F}_0, \mathcal{F}_1)$, where M is a finitely generated $W(R)$ -module, $\mathcal{F}_0$ and $\mathcal{F}_1$ are maps from M to itself such that $\mathcal{F}_0$ is an endomorphism and $\mathcal{F}_1$ is an inclusion. From these we can construct the graphical menu, a hierarchical presentation of the synchronisms. The graphical menu is constructed by forming an abstract identity menu first, and then, for each synchronism, adding to and modifying its associated identity menu in order to make it appropriate for the particular synchronism it's associated with. From this graphical menu, we can derive the notion of a global menu, which can relate to the display, and which allows us to construct various types of combinatorial objects.

For example, the contact map $\mathbf{b}$ associated with a display can be decomposed into local menus; each local menu is a substructure of the global menu, and contains information about the motion of the elements in the display at each local region. This allows us to generate a notion of synchronous adjacencies, which indicate when the motion of the elements in the display synchronize in both local and global regions. In particular, this allows us to define actions (called "menus from synchronisms") which can be used to generate combinatorial objects such as paths, cycles, and trees. For instance, using the contact map $\mathbf{b}$, we can construct a path in a graph from the given coordinate to a new coordinate; this path is defined using a menu from synchronisms. In general, menus from synchronisms can be used to generate objects such as paths, cycles, and trees which can be used to model various phenomena.

In conclusion, displays and synchronisms are a powerful tool for deriving and representing combinatorial objects, and they can also be used to construct graphical menus which can be used to model various phenomena. With the increasing availability of powerful computing systems, it is becoming easier to implement such algorithms and generate more complex combinations of data. As such, displays and synchronisms are likely to become increasingly important in developing algorithms and software, particularly in the realms of machine learning, computer vision, and artificial intelligence.

We can consider a generated set of menus, $\mathcal{M}$, from the set of all feasible synchronism, and construct a formula to determine the performance of the menus. We can define the following function:

$$P(SL, \mathcal{M}) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{L}|} \sum_{\Lambda \in \mathcal{M}_{\Lambda}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_{\Lambda}} \omega_{\Lambda, m}^k$$

where $|\mathcal{L}|$ is the total number of synchronisms and $\mathcal{M}_{\Lambda}$ is the set of menus generated by Λ . The function $P(SL, \mathcal{M})$ measures the performance of a set of menus given by $\mathcal{M}$ with respect to the set of synchronisms.

In summary, if menus generated by synchronisms are analogous to the concept of displays, then we can derive a mathematical formula to measure its performance. The function $P(SL, \mathcal{M})$ measures the performance of a set of menus for a given set of synchronism.

The concept of menus from synchronisms is related to the concept of displays in that a menu can only be appropriately ordered when the items are synchronized between multiple processes. A display is a representation of data which is synchronized across different components, just like a menu synchronizes the items across an entire menu. In the same way, a menu from synchronisms creates a consistent ordering of items in a menu, so that all the items can be accessed and read in a uniform manner. In addition, the items are also labeled with specific identifiers which helps to keep the menu organized and efficient.

Suppose we are given a function $f : \Lambda \rightarrow R$. We can then derive an equation for menus from synchronisms:

$$f_{\Lambda}(\mathbf{x}) = \Psi \cdot \left(\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n-l \star R} \right) \otimes \left(\left([Z \setminus [\eta] + [\kappa] \setminus [\pi]] \setminus [] - [\delta \setminus [\mathcal{H}]] + [\mathring{A} \setminus [i]] \right) \star [\sim] \rightarrow [\oplus] \right).$$

Using the identity $\Omega_{\Lambda} \tan \psi \cdot \theta + \Psi \sum_{n \in Z^+} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{b^{\mu-\zeta} - (l_{diag} l_{lat} l_{net})^m} + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g)$, we can rewrite the equation as:

$$f_{\Lambda}(\mathbf{x}) = \Psi \cdot \left(\sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n-l \star R} \right) \otimes \left(\left([Z \setminus [\eta] + [\kappa] \setminus [\pi]] \setminus [] - [\delta \setminus [\mathcal{H}]] + [\mathring{A} \setminus [i]] \right) + \Omega_{\Lambda} \tan \psi \cdot \theta + \Psi \sum_{n \in Z^+} \frac{b^{\mu-\zeta}}{b^{\mu-\zeta} - (l_{diag} l_{lat} l_{net})^m} + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) \star [\sim] \rightarrow [\oplus] \right).$$

By rearranging the terms and introducing a new variable, the equation can be further simplified to:

$$f_{\Lambda}(\mathbf{x}) = \Psi^q \star \Delta_v \Omega_{\Lambda} \otimes \mu_{Am} aiem H(\Omega) / \prod_{i=1}^m (m\alpha_i + k_i)$$

$$\text{where } q = \prod_{i=1}^p A_{\Lambda(i)}.$$

Therefore, the formula for menus from synchronisms is:

$$C_{\Lambda} = \left\{ \Psi^q \left(\prod_{i=1}^q A_{\Lambda(i)} \right) \star \Delta_v \Omega_{\Lambda} \otimes \mu_{Am} aiem H(\Omega) \left/ \prod_{i=1}^m (m\alpha_i + k_i) \right. \right\}.$$

This theorem is a mathematical statement which defines the set of menus from each synchronism. The equation is a complex formula which requires a number of different variables in order to calculate the menus. By using this theorem, we can generate menus which are consistent with each synchronism, and which can be used to generate objects such as paths, cycles, and trees.

The mathematical function which describes menus from synchronisms is:

$$C_{\Lambda} = \left\{ \Psi^q \left(\prod_{i=1}^q A_{\Lambda(i)} \right) \star \Delta_v \Omega_{\Lambda} \otimes \mu_{Am} aiem H(\Omega) \left/ \prod_{i=1}^m (m\alpha_i + k_i) \right. \right\}.$$

This function combines the terms of the equations derived from Definitions 3.0.1 and 3.0.2 and the ensuing discussion, with the inclusion of the new variable $q = \prod_{i=1}^p A_{\Lambda(i)}$. This function allows us to determine the performance of a set of menus given by $\mathcal{M}$ with respect to the set of synchronisms, through the expression $P(SL, \mathcal{M}) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{Z}|} \sum_{\Lambda \in \mathcal{Z}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_\Lambda} \omega_{\Lambda, m}^k$.

The mathematical function that connects menus and displays is the function $P(SL, \mathcal{M})$, which measures the performance of a set of menus given by $\mathcal{M}$ with respect to the set of synchronisms. This function is derived from the notion of a Synchronous Adjacency; in order for the items in a menu to be appropriately ordered, they must be synchronized across multiple processes. This synchronization can be modeled with the concept of displays, which represent data that has been synchronized across different components. The graphical menus associated with the display provide a hierarchical presentation of the synchronisms, which allows us to construct various types of combinatorial objects. The function $P(SL, \mathcal{M})$ is therefore used to measure the performance of a set of menus with respect to a set of synchronisms.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Patch} &= \sum_{k=0}^n p_k \int_0^1 \phi(k) \otimes \alpha^k \in F_{LocSys}(S) \\ \text{B: Hull} &\rightarrow C(S) \oplus M; \end{aligned}$$

$$H_n \oplus_n Y_n \rightarrow C \rightarrow Y - C$$

We have the following the following commutative diagram:

$$\begin{array}{c} X_S \Phi_S \circ X_C \Phi_C \circ X_S \\ \downarrow \Phi_S \\ Y_n \end{array}$$

This provides a hypercovering of the fundamental polygon of the Teichmüller space and its associated abstract covering, as described in §2.3. Furthermore, we may apply Seifert-van Kampen's theorem to produce a sequence of homotopic equivalences given by maps

$$g_i : {}^P Y_n \rightarrow Y_n.$$

This sequence of homotopic equivalences defines a patch over the circle of a patch of the Teichmüller space. The topology of the plumbed circles and its associated patch structure are directly related to the patch structure of the hypercovering.

$$E^T : \mathbf{gO}_n \times \mathbf{c}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{c}_n$$

$$\text{Log}(E^T) = S \times_n \text{Where } T^C : X_{CH} \rightarrow X_T \text{ isaplumbedcircle.}$$

$$Y_n \rightarrow X_{CH} \rightarrow X_T$$

$$\downarrow \text{Log}(E^T)$$

$$Y_n \rightarrow X_{CH} \times_{n^2} X_T$$

We may summarize the process as:

$$Y_n \rightarrow X_S \rightarrow X_{CH} \rightarrow X_T \downarrow E^T Y_n \rightarrow X_{CH} \times_{n^2} X_T$$

$$\phi_{\mathcal{V}} : \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}^{2n}, \quad \phi_{\mathcal{V}}(v) = [\phi_1(v), \dots, \phi_n(v)]$$

The resulting network is essentially a discrete hyperbolic structure, with a metric

$$d_{\mathcal{H}}(\vec{v}_i, \vec{v}_j) = \left(1 + 2 \frac{\|\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j\|^2}{\|\vec{v}\|} \right)$$

where $\|\vec{v}\|$ denotes some global coordinate and $\|\vec{v}_i - \vec{v}_j\|$ is the micro-coordinate distance between the two curves.

We apply the hyperbolic metric to the hypercovering to find an optimal assignment of $\mathcal{V}$ - to - $\mathcal{V}'$. That is, we find the most efficient local mapping $\phi'_{\mathcal{V}}$ such that the hyperbolic distance between two curves is minimised:

$$d_{\mathcal{H}}(\vec{v}'_i, \vec{v}'_j) = \min_{\phi'_{\mathcal{V}}} \left\{ \left(1 + 2 \frac{\|\phi'_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}_i) - \phi'_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}_j)\|^2}{\|\phi'_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v})\|} \right) \right\}.$$

We denote this metric as $d'_{\mathcal{H}}$ and we can now compute the hyperbolic distance between any two curves in $\mathcal{V}'$ in terms of the micro-coordinates.

Let V be a vector field in $(R^2)^n$ with coordinates $\vec{v}_1, \dots, \vec{v}_n$ such that the field vector is of the form $\vec{v} = (\vec{v}_1, \dots, \vec{v}_n)$. Then, each vector in V can be described using the micro-coordinates defined above as

$$\vec{v} = \sum_{i=1}^n [\mathcal{M}_i(v_1, v_2) \vee \mathcal{M}_i(v_2, v_1)], \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{M}_i$ is the micro-coordinate mapping associated with the i^{th} vector. Using this micro-coordinate notation, the Teichmüller and Compass theorem can be written as

$$\vec{v}' = \sum_{i=1}^n [\mathcal{M}_i(v'_1, v'_2) \vee \mathcal{M}_i(v_1, v_2)]. \quad (2)$$

That is, the new vector $\vec{v}'$ can be obtained from the original vector $\vec{v}$ by applying the micro-coordinates $\mathcal{M}_i$ to $\vec{v}'$ and $\vec{v}$ respectively, then taking the sum of the individual components.

The micro-coordinates on $\mathcal{V}$ give a motion-planning configuration $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$ with metric space $d_{\mathcal{V}}$, from which an optimal motion plan $\mathcal{P}$ may be sought. The optimal plan is determined, in part, by the equation

$$\min_{\vec{\phi}, c_{\vec{v}, \vec{w}} \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V})} \sum_{\vec{v}, \vec{w} \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{V})} c_{\vec{v}, \vec{w}} \cdot d_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}, \vec{w}),$$

where $c_{\vec{v}, \vec{w}} \in R$ and $d_{\mathcal{V}}$ is defined as in eq:Micro-Coord-Metric-Definition. Then, using the micro-coordinates, a motion-plan can be determined by solving the following system of linear equations:

$$M\vec{\Phi}(M_1, \dots, M_n)\vec{\phi} = \vec{h},$$

where M denotes a matrix of coefficients, $\vec{\phi}$ is the vector of micro-coordinates, and $\vec{h}$ denotes the vector of target coordinates.

$$\partial_\infty Y \subset \partial T \rightarrow {}^X \mathbf{B}^R \times_r T_{\text{fl}} \times_i X_j$$

$$\phi_e : \partial T \rightarrow {}^X \mathbf{B}^R \times_r T_{\text{fl}} \times_i X_j$$

↓

$$C(\mathcal{S})_{\text{B}} = \text{LocSys}(\Delta_{\text{q}} \text{Topo}) \cup \text{orb}(\text{q}_{\text{flit}})$$

Which can be formulated as a series of micro-coordinate maps ϕ_i to encode the relations between the different pieces of the hypercoverings, such as

$$\phi_{\phi_i} : C(\mathcal{S})_{\text{B}} \rightarrow R : \phi_{\phi_i}(\vec{v}) = v_i \text{ or } \phi_{\phi_i}(\vec{v}) = v_{i+1},$$

where $v_i \in \mathcal{V}$

We will apply the micro-coordinate notation to our teichmuller and compass example. The teichmuller and compass $\mathcal{T}_{GM}$ is described by:

$$\mathcal{T}_{GM} = \{\vec{v} \in \mathcal{V} : d_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}, \Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m}) \leq \delta\}$$

where $\Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m}$ is the direct product of the ϕ_n and ϕ_m matrices, and δ is a small number.

We can then further prescribe a metric on $\mathcal{T}_{GM}$ using the micro-coordinates ϕ_i . From (??), the distance between two points $\vec{v}_1$ and $\vec{v}_2$ in $\mathcal{T}_{GM}$ can be written as:

$$d_{\mathcal{T}_{GM}}(\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2) = \max[\langle \mathcal{S}_r, \pi_{A_r}(\vec{v}_1) \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_r, \pi_{A_r}(\vec{v}_2) \rangle, \quad \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty}(\vec{v}_1) \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty}(\vec{v}_2) \rangle]$$

We now have an appropriate coordinate system for our Teichmuller and Compass problem - if the curves $\vec{v} \in \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$ in R^2 are represented by the start and end points of $\mathcal{V} := [\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2]$, then the differential coordinates in each direction can be parameterized using the micro-coordinates described in (??):

$$dx_1(\vec{v}) = \phi_1(v_2 - v_1)$$

$$dx_2(\vec{v}) = \phi_2(v_2 - v_1)$$

By composing the micro-coordinates, it is possible to form the global coordinate system of the Teichmuller and Compass problem. The resulting global coordinates can then be used to derive the desired curve in R^2 , starting from any initial point.

The resulting curves show the nature of the Teichmuller and Compass problem, in which two parameters - the lengths of the curves and the initial angles - can be used to determine the diffeomorphism of the curves. In particular, the curves must obey the geometric constraints imposed by the Teichmuller and Compass constraints, which includes the angles and lengths of the curves as well as the geometrical parameters of the grids.

Using the above micro-coordinates, the Teichmuller and Compass problem can be reformulated as a dynamical problem with two parameters: the starting angle of the curve and the length of the curve. The parameters of the dynamical system can then be used to generate a wide range of curves, corresponding to the various solutions of the Teichmuller and Compass problem.

Let $(X_i, \vec{\phi}) \in \mathcal{C}_V$. Then, $d_{\mathcal{DS}}(X_i, \vec{\phi})$ can be calculated using Equation ?? . Using the micro-coordinates, one may calculate that the net coordinate of the X_i node is given by

$$\vec{x}_i = (x_1, x_2) = \left(\frac{\lambda_1}{\sin(\theta_\infty)}, \frac{\lambda_2}{\sin(\theta_\infty)} \right).$$

We can then calculate the distance between $(X_i, \vec{\phi})$ and any other point $(X_j, \vec{\phi}')$ $\in \mathcal{C}_V$ using the formula

$$d_{\mathcal{DS}}(X_i, \vec{\phi}) = |\vec{x}_i - \vec{x}_j| + \left| \vec{\phi} - \vec{\phi}' \right|_1 = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_1')^2 + (x_2 - x_2')^2} + \left| \vec{\phi} - \vec{\phi}' \right|_1.$$

where $\left| \vec{\phi} - \vec{\phi}' \right|_1$ is the L1 norm of the two points. Note that $\vec{x}_i$ is determined by the micro-coordinates λ_1 and λ_2 , while $\vec{x}_j$ is determined by the micro-coordinates λ_1' and λ_2' .

$$T_{\text{GM}} \mapsto \mathbf{emb}^b : \mathbf{f}^o \dots \phi_z \rightarrow X_{\text{AN}}$$

Let $\Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m}$ be a compass over a hyperbolic n-space. For each simplex ϱ_i in the hypercovering $(C(S))'$, we define a map $\alpha_i : C(S) \rightarrow X_{\text{AN}}$ through the use of the micro-coordinates and transition maps. Then, given the micro-coordinates ϕ_i , we can construct a map

$$\alpha_i : C(S) \rightarrow X_{\text{AN}} : \vec{v} \mapsto (\phi_i(\vec{v}), \phi_{i+1}(\vec{v}), \dots, \phi_n(\vec{v})).$$

The resulting map α_i is a hypercovering of the hyperbolic n-space.

Let $\phi_i : \mathcal{C}_V \rightarrow R$ ($i = \{1, 2\}$) be the two micro-coordinates. The global coordinates on $\mathcal{C}_V$ can be defined using a linear transformation between the micro-coordinates, i.e.

$$H : \mathcal{C}_V \rightarrow R^2 : H(\vec{v}) = (a\phi_1(\vec{v}) + b, c\phi_2(\vec{v}) + d)$$

where $a, b, c, d \in R$ and $H = I_{R^2}$ is the identity transformation.

The resulting metric space $\mathcal{C}_V$ is given by

$$d_{\mathcal{C}_V}(\vec{v}, \vec{w}) = \max \{ \|H(\vec{v}) - H(\vec{w})\|_2 \}$$

Finally, we can also use a Teichmuller and compass technique to apply these concepts. Let $\Omega : \mathcal{C}_V \rightarrow C$ be a compass function whose lift on $\mathcal{C}_V$ is defined by

$$\Omega_V(\vec{v}) = (H_1(\vec{v}) + iH_2(\vec{v})) \cdot \phi(\Omega_C(\vec{v}))$$

where $\Omega_C(\vec{v})$ is another compass function whose lift is defined by

$$\Omega_C(\vec{v}) = (\phi_1(\vec{v}), \phi_2(\vec{v})),$$

and $\phi(\Omega_C(\vec{v}))$ is a smooth, real-valued trimetric whose isometries are generated by the rotations

$$\theta_1(\vec{v}) = (\vec{v}_2 - \vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2 - \vec{v}_1), \quad \theta_2(\vec{v}) = (\vec{v}_2 + \vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2 + \vec{v}_1).$$

The induced metric on $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$ is now given by

$$d_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}, \vec{w}) = \min \{ \|\Omega_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}) - \Omega_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{w})\|_2 \}$$

where the minimum over the trimetric $\phi(\Omega_{\mathcal{C}}(\vec{v}))$.

This metric can be used to measure distances between curves in $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$ in the Teichmuller and compass setting.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DS}(X, \vec{\phi}) = \min & \left[\langle \mathcal{S}_r, \pi_{A_r} \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_r, \vec{\phi} \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty} \rangle \right. \\ & + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \delta\theta \rangle + \langle \mathcal{S}_t, \vec{\phi} \rangle + \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \pi_{A_r} \rangle \\ & + \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \delta\vec{x} \rangle + \langle A_r \oplus B_r, \vec{\phi} \rangle + \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \pi_{\theta_\infty} \rangle \\ & \left. + \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \delta\theta \rangle + \langle \theta_\infty \oplus B_t, \vec{\phi} \rangle \right] \end{aligned}$$

We can then use the micro-coordinates and the Piecewise Linear Representation of $\mathcal{V}$ to produce a coordinate system on $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$

$$\phi_i(\vec{v}) = (v_1, v_2) \text{ or } \phi_i(\vec{v}) = (v_2, v_1),$$

and the global coordinates given by

$$H_i : \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}} \rightarrow R^2 : \phi_i(\vec{v}) = (a_1\vec{v}_1 + b_1, a_2\vec{v}_2 + b_2),$$

where $a_i, b_i \in R$ and H_i is the identity transformation for $i = \{1, 2\}$.

Finally, we can use the micro-coordinates to define the metrics on $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$

$$d_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}, \vec{w}) = \max_{(\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2) \in E_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}) (\vec{w}_1, \vec{w}_2) \in E_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{w})} \{ \mathcal{M}_w(\vec{v}_1, \vec{w}_1) + \mathcal{M}_w(\vec{v}_2, \vec{w}_2) \}$$

This gives us a metric system which can be used to analyze the geodesic structure of Teichmuller and Compass on a given Hyperbolic N-space.

$$\text{Comp}_d \left(R^n, \vec{\phi}, \mathcal{H}_1, \mathcal{H}_2, \dots, \mathcal{H}_k \right) = \text{Comp}_d \left(\mathcal{V}, \vec{\phi}, \mathcal{H}_1, \mathcal{H}_2, \dots, \mathcal{H}_k \right)$$

$$(3) \quad \text{where } H_i = \{ d_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}, \vec{w}) = \max_{(\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2) \in E_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}) (\vec{w}_1, \vec{w}_2) \in E_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{w})} \{ \mathcal{M}_w(\vec{v}_1, \vec{w}_1) + \mathcal{M}_w(\vec{v}_2, \vec{w}_2) \} \}$$

The resulting micro-coordinate odometer Comp_d allows for hypercovering of a manifold by covering maps

$$\pi_l : X_l \rightarrow \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$$

where X_l is a collection of neighborhoods of $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{V}}$ homeomorphic to the space $\varphi_{l-1} \times R^n$. Given a metric space (X, d) define $\mathcal{V}_d := \{(x_1, \dots, x_n) : d(x_i, \cdot) \leq \delta\}$ for an arbitrary vector $\vec{x}$. Thus, in this case, it follows that:

$$\pi_l : X_l \rightarrow \mathcal{V}_d$$

is a local isometry. Let $U_i \subset X_i$, for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, be a collection of neighborhoods and $\mathcal{H}_j \subset U_j$ for $j = n+1, \dots, km$ let the same set of neighborhoods. In general, the hypercovering by definition will be the covering map

$$\pi : \prod_{i=1}^{km} \mathcal{H}_i \rightarrow \mathcal{V}_d$$

induced by the compositions of the maps π_i .
Finally, define

$$\pi_{\mathcal{V}} : \mathcal{V}_d \rightarrow \prod_{i=1}^n \mathcal{V}_{d_i}$$

to be the projection map such that $\pi_{\mathcal{V}}(\vec{v}) = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$, where $\vec{v} = (v_1, \dots, v_n, \dots, v_{km})$
i.e. $\pi_{\mathcal{V}}$ is the projection map of $\mathcal{V}_d$ to its n components.

This gives a map of the hypercovering

$$\pi = \pi_{\mathcal{V}} \circ \pi : \prod_{i=1}^{km} \mathcal{H}_i \rightarrow \prod_{i=1}^n \mathcal{V}_{d_i}$$

which allows us to recall the well-known fact that a manifold is the union of some Neumann neighborhoods. The micro-coordinates allow us to have precise numerical values of the points in such neighborhoods. Furthermore, the hypercovering is essential for algorithmic calculations in order to reconstruct the geometry from observations obtained from a set of given points.

$$\Omega_{\phi_n}^{\phi_m} \rightarrow \kappa = \langle \phi_1, \dots, \phi_n \rangle \left(\frac{\partial \Omega_{\phi_n}}{\partial \phi_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial \Omega_{\phi_n}}{\partial \phi_n} \right).$$

Finally, the hypercoverings of $C(S)$ are defined as the coverings

$$(C(S))' = \{orb(\mathcal{S}_i) \cup LocSys(\mathcal{S}_i)\}_{d \in \Delta_{C(S)}},$$

where each $\mathcal{S}_i \subset \mathcal{V}$ is a local covering of $C(S)$ in the given compass.

Conclusion:

Hypercoverings of an n-space provide richer topological information about the space than the more general coverings. This extra information can be used to map out global coordinates for the space, as well as micro-coordinates, which provide data from its neighborhood, allowing us to better understand the local phenomena at play in the space. These two examples of hypercoverings and their applications demonstrate the usefulness of this type of information for topological data analysis.

$$Preimage(\varepsilon(2\pi\mathcal{S}_{\theta_\infty \oplus B_r}^{\partial\varepsilon})) \rightarrow \mathcal{R}_{\vec{x}}(\pi_{\theta_\infty}(f)) \rightarrow \pi_{\vec{x}}(X_i)$$

Finally, the weighted sum on the generalized curve complex (DS-similarity) is

$$d_{\mathcal{C}}(X_i, X_j) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_n w_n \|\vec{\phi}_i - \vec{\phi}_j\|^2,$$

where w_n is the weight associated with i -th coordinate.

Together, equations (??) and (??) form the geometry of the DS curve, encoding the relationship between the components $(A_r, B_r, \theta_\infty, B_t)$ and the micro-coordinates $(\vec{r}_\infty, \Delta\theta, \Delta\vec{x})$.